

An Assessment of Emotional Maturity of Adolescent Belonging to Nuclear and Joint Family Type

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Abstract: The present study is aimed to investigate emotional maturity of late adolescent girls and boys belonging to nuclear and joint family type. For this purpose, sample of 120 boys (60 joint family & 60 nuclear family) and 120 girls (60 joint family & 60 nuclear family) were taken from Udaipur city. For this purpose emotional maturity scale by Dr. Yashvir Singh and Mahesh Bhargava is used. Frequency and percentage method is employed to statistically analyse the data. The result reveals that there is a significant difference in emotional maturity of boys and girls adolescent. The result reveals both joint and nuclear family boys are socially stable and girls of joint family type are socially instable and nuclear family girls are found to be extremely unstable in autonomous functioning domain.

Keywords: Emotional Maturity, Nuclear Family, Joint Family, Adolescent Boys, Adolescent Girls.

1. INTRODUCTION

Family is the most significant and primary unit of society having a strong influence upon the emotional development of an individual. Family is typically a context that reinforces adult values, promotes school success and supports emotional maturity. It offers affection and security and operates as a role defining agency, central to promoting the maturity of an adolescent and determining his future adjustment as an adult. So a greater degree of family interaction especially with the adolescent is developmentally beneficial (Larson and Richards, 1991). Late adolescence is marked by transition from highly dependent and controlled period of childhood into a period of increasing sense of self-exploration and autonomy (Wentzel and Battle, 2001). Specifically, adolescents begin to develop their self-concept and explore their relationship and connection to family, friends, and the larger society (Simmons *et al.*, 1987). Parents can be both facilitators and inhibitors of their children's psychological development. Parental acceptance plays a major role in determining the attitude and behaviour of the child and the accepted child is generally well socialized, co-operative, friendly, loyal, emotionally stable and careful (Kiran & Singh, 1982). Family relationships generally alter as the process of differentiation begins to take place. This is a time when adolescents rely more on peers, seek increased independence, and are less willing to see themselves as part of a hierarchy that is headed by their parents (Collins & Repinski, 1994). In families where relationships are seriously attenuated, however, peer influence surges and adolescents are at greater risk for adjustment problems (Fulgini & Eccles, 1993). Several researchers share the general hypothesis that parent adolescence interactions that encouraged differentiation and also sent a message of acceptance and connection facilitate positive outcomes including healthy identity, perspective taking skills, ego development and self-esteem with continued emotional dependence on family, particularly on mother. The normative task in adolescence could be the same for both boys and girls to develop a healthy balance between autonomy and ties with parents but it is more of a challenge to disengage from the parents for the girls than it is for boys.

In our culture, boys experience more conflict with their parents and are less likely to accept parental regulations as appropriate, whereas girls are more emotionally dependent on their parents. Sexual roles and gender differences lay different paths for boys and girls in developing autonomy. Research on gender differences in development of autonomy reveals several inconsistencies. Douvan (1963) suggested that boys develop autonomous behaviour more rapidly than girls.

On the other hand, literature of Steinberg and Silverberg (1987) found emotional autonomy during early adolescence to be greater among girls, with girls scoring high on self-reliance scales. There also exist cross-cultural differences in the development of autonomy.

In India, parent's views are generally accepted. Kakar (1978) observed that the strong ties to family continue into adulthood. Indian girls spend much less time with peers as they are given less freedom of movement. Researches state that the traditional, affectionate, religious and economic bonds that create family cohesion are weakening. "Nucleation has depleted the emotional surround of the individuals". Indian adolescents are gradually moving to achieve autonomy and reducing dependency on parents.

Adolescents are facing enhanced difficulties due to fierce competition, peer pressures and parental expectations in addition to daily rigors of life. This is quite evident from the increase in the number of criminal, suicidal, drug abuse and rape cases. To meet the new demands and to adjust with the new roles and responsibilities proper guidance and motivation from parents, family and teachers is required for adequate emotional development.

2. OBJECTIVE

To study emotional maturity of late adolescent boys and girls belonging to nuclear and joint family.

3. METHODOLOGY

The sample for the present study consisted of 240 respondents, 120 boys and 120 girls within the age range of 16-18 years. Sample of 60 boys and 60 girls from nuclear and joint family structure was taken respectively. The respondents belonged to government co-ed school of Udaipur district and were selected using random sampling method without replacement method.

Emotional maturity scale developed by Singh and Bhargava (1990) was used to find out the information regarding adolescents' emotional maturity level. The statements in scale were related to five major areas with 48 items. The first 10 items examined emotional instability, the second 10 items examined emotional regression, the third 10 items assessed social maladjustment, the fourth 10 items assessed personality disintegration and the last 8 items examined lack of independence. Frequency and percentage distribution was done for statistical analysis of overall emotional maturity of adolescent boys and girls.

Table 1: Distribution of boys from joint family in dimensions of emotional maturity

n=60

S. No.	Dimensions of emotional maturity	BOYS (Joint family)			
		Extremely stable f (%)	Moderately stable f (%)	Unstable f (%)	Extremely unstable f (%)
1.	Emotional stability	30 (50)	14 (23.34)	11 (18.33)	5 (8.33)
2.	Emotional progression	28 (46.67)	11 (18.33)	9 (15)	12 (20)
3.	Social stability	42 (70)	5 (8.33)	8 (13.34)	5 (8.33)
4.	Personality integration	33 (55)	4 (6.67)	12 (20)	11 (18.33)
5.	Autonomous functioning	27 (45)	14 (23.33)	13 (21.67)	6 (10)
	Overall emotional maturity	30 (50)	10 (16.67)	10 (16.67)	10 (16.66)

Table 1 depicts that half of the boys of joint family were extremely emotionally stable . 46.67% of the boys had extremely stable emotional progression. One fifth (20%) of the male respondents of joint family were extremely unstable in this particular dimension. 70% of boys from joint family were extremely socially stable followed by equal percentage of (8.33%) respondents in moderately stable and extremely unstable category. More than half of the subjects possessed extremely stable personality integration whereas very few had moderately stable personality integration. Furthermore, the table depict that 45 per cent of respondents were extremely stable in autonomous functioning component of emotional maturity. It can be inferred from the table that maximum percentage of boys from joint family were stable in all the components of emotional maturity with majority in social stability dimension. Though globalisation has led to acculturation of traditional joint family system, yet the change is gradual. Still, there are many families who follow patriarchal norms according to which males are the head of the family. Boys reared in such family perceive older male members as role model. They learn to cater to the family's needs and responsibilities at a very young age, hence becoming more emotionally and socially stable. The findings are in line with Hay *et al.*, (2000) who identified that parent relationships have a significant influence on males than females' emotional and social stability.

50% of the boys from joint family had extremely stable emotional maturity whereas percentage of respondents in other three categories of emotional maturity i.e., moderately stable, unstable and extremely unstable was found to be equal (16.67%).

Table 2: Distribution of boys from nuclear family in dimensions of emotional maturity

n=60

S. No.	Dimensions of emotional maturity	BOYS (Nuclear family)			
		Extremely stable f (%)	Moderately stable f (%)	Unstable f (%)	Extremely unstable f (%)
1.	Emotional Stability	17 (28.33)	15 (25)	22 (36.67)	6 (10)
2.	Emotional Progression	17 (28.33)	22 (36.67)	14 (23.33)	7 (11.67)
3.	Social Stability	39 (65)	6 (10)	10 (16.67)	5 (8.33)
4.	Personality Integration	22 (36.67)	12 (20)	17 (28.33)	9 (15)
5.	Autonomous functioning	13 (21.67)	27 (45)	13 (21.67)	7 (11.66)
	Overall emotional maturity	(25)	(35)	(31.67)	(8.33)

A perusal of Table 2 shows that maximum percentage (36.67%) of boys from nuclear family were emotionally unstable followed by 28.33 per cent with extremely stable emotionality. Only 10 per cent were found to be extremely unstable in emotional stability component. It further reveals that 36.67 per cent had moderately stable emotional progression. More than one fourth and less than one fourth were found to be extremely stable and unstable in this dimension respectively. Majority (65%) of the boys had extremely stable social stability whereas a meagre (8.33%) per cent of respondents were socially unstable. Maximum percentage (36.67%) of respondents had extremely stable in personality integration followed by 28.33 per cent falling in unstable category. It is clearly evident that equal percentage (21.67%) of subjects lie in extremely stable and unstable category of autonomous functioning component and 45 per cent had moderately stable autonomy.

Data projected in Table 2 presents the fact that in nuclear family boys are socially stable because due to presence of less elderly figure they may have to take more risks and face more challenges and hence they have to adjust and manage to social situation by themselves only. Moreover, they receive more opportunities and stimulating environment to experiment with their emotions and are given more freedom which helps them to gain a better understanding of the world.

Table 3: Distribution of girls from joint family in dimensions of emotional maturity

n=60

S. No.	Dimensions of emotional maturity	GIRLS (Joint family)			
		Extremely stable f (%)	Moderately stable f (%)	Unstable f (%)	Extremely unstable f (%)
1.	Emotional stability	11 (18.33)	11 (18.33)	13 (21.67)	25 (41.67)
2.	Emotional progression	13 (21.67)	11 (18.33)	19 (31.67)	17 (28.33)
3.	Social stability	33 (55)	7 (11.66)	10 (16.67)	10 (16.67)
4.	Personality integration	16 (26.67)	10 (16.66)	16 (26.67)	18 (30)
5.	Autonomous functioning	19 (31.67)	8 (13.33)	14 (23.33)	19 (31.67)
	Overall emotional maturity	8 (13.33)	16 (26.67)	11 (18.33)	25 (41.67)

Equal percentages (18.33%) of girls from joint family had extremely and moderately stable emotional stability whereas maximum numbers of respondents were extremely emotionally unstable. 31.67 per cent of respondents were found to have unstable emotional progression followed by 28.33 per cent lying in extremely unstable category. More than one fifth had extremely stable emotional progression. It also shows that more than half of the girls of joint family had extremely stable social stability and an equal percentage (16.67%) of subjects in unstable and extremely unstable category. Very few (11.66%) fell in moderately stable category of social stability component. In personality integration component of emotional maturity, equal number of respondents (26.67%) lie in extremely stable and unstable category, respectively. Almost 30 per cent of females from joint family had extremely unstable personality integration. Equal percentage of respondents had extremely stable and extremely unstable autonomous functioning. Less than one fourth were unstable and 13.33 per cent were moderately stable in this component.

Girls are always expected to make adjustments to new patterns of behaviour and social expectations due to which they experience emotional instability. Research by (Salovey *et al.*, 2002) showed that lower levels of emotional clarity are correlated with higher likelihood of experiencing adjustment related problems. In joint families girls receive more punishment as compared to boys; the reason may be the traditional stereotyped families who expect more from girls regarding their traits, roles, responsibilities, and obligation. Hence girls are portrayed as symbol of perfection. Corporal punishment in the form of beating and spanking has been understood to predict increased antisocial behaviour of children and adolescence and at an increasingly greater level with age (Gershoff *et al.*, 2010; Grogan-kaylor, 2005). Critical examination of the table reveals that 41.67 per cent of girls from joint family were found to possess extremely unstable emotional maturity followed by 26.67 per cent having moderately stable emotional maturity. Very few (13.33%) had extremely stable emotional maturity followed by 18.33 with unstable emotional maturity. According to Devadas and Jaya (2007) with increased social and personal experiences and with increased ability to think rationally, the older adolescents see himself, family, friends and life in general in a more realistic way and are emotionally mature, in contrast to this, data shows that majority of the respondents are 16 years of age which may be the reason behind their emotional immaturity.

Table 4: Distribution of girls from nuclear family in dimensions of emotional maturity

n=60

S. No.	Dimensions of emotional maturity	GIRLS (Nuclear family)			
		Extremely stable f (%)	Moderately stable f (%)	Unstable f (%)	Extremely unstable f (%)
1.	Emotional stability	5 (8.33)	10 (16.67)	14 (23.33)	31 (51.67)
2.	Emotional progression	12 (20)	7 (11.66)	19 (31.67)	22 (36.67)

3.	Social stability	23 (38.33)	14 (23.33)	16 (26.67)	7 (11.67)
4.	Personality integration	14 (23.33)	13 (21.67)	11 (18.33)	22 (36.67)
5.	Autonomous functioning	14 (23.33)	11 (18.33)	15 (25)	20 (33.34)
	Overall emotional maturity	7 (11.67)	11 (18.33)	20 (33.33)	22 (36.67)

Table 4 depict that more than half of the girls from nuclear family were found to be extremely emotionally unstable and 23.33 per cent were emotionally unstable. Very few (8.33%) were extremely emotionally stable with a slight increase (16.67) in percentage of respondents in moderately stable category of emotional stability. In emotional progression component of emotional maturity majority of the subjects were unstable with a very few percentages (11.66%) in moderately stable category. One fifth were found to have extremely stable emotional progression. Table 4.6 further indicates that a very good percentage (38.33%) lie in the extremely stable category of social stability component followed by 26.67 per cent in unstable category. More than one fifth were moderately stable socially and 11.67 were extremely socially unstable. Table revealed that 36.67 per cent of respondents were found to have extremely unstable personality integration followed by 23.33 per cent in extremely stable category. 21.67 per cent possessed moderately stable personality followed by 18.33 per cent with unstable personality integration. Table 4.6 is indicative of the fact that girls are not given much autonomy with maximum percentage (33.34%) of girls in extremely unstable category of autonomous functioning. One fourth of the respondents had unstable autonomy followed by 23.33 per cent having extremely stable autonomy. The Table depicts that girls enjoy less autonomy. This may be due to the reason that majority of the respondents have middle birth order and it is believed that they have a less well defined self-esteem and are somewhat overlooked. They are not special traditional patriarchal families impose higher demands on females about their role, responsibilities, traits etc. Decisions are generally made for them. They have no identity as an individual, no right to express their feelings, uniqueness or to develop autonomy. On the other hand, they were found to be more stable in social stability component in comparison to other dimensions. In overall emotional maturity, 36.67 per cent of girls from nuclear family were extremely unstable and one third of the sample had unstable emotional maturity. Only 11.67 per cent were found to have extremely stable emotional maturity followed by 18.33 per cent in moderately stable category.

4. CONCLUSION

The present study highlights the relationship between emotional maturity and family type. It is found that boys hailing from joint family type are more emotionally stable whereas on the contrary boys belonging to nuclear family are more emotionally unstable. Joint family girls were more emotionally unstable in comparison to nuclear family girls.

REFERENCES

- [1] Collins, W. A. and Repinski, D. J. 1994. Relationships during Adolescence: Continuity and Change in Interpersonal Perspective. In Montemayor, R., Adams, G. R., and Gullotta, T. P. (Eds.). *Personal Relationships during Adolescence*. Thousand Oaks. Sage Publications. pp7-36.
- [2] Devadas, R. P. and Jaya, N. 2007. *A Textbook on Child Development*. Macmillan: India Ltd. pp128-137.
- [3] Douvan, E. 1963. Employment and the Adolescent, In F.I. Nye and L.W. Hoffman (Eds.): *The Employed Mother in America*. Chicago: Rand McNally and Company.
- [4] Fuligni, A. J. and Eccles, J. S. 1993. Perceived Parent-Child Relationships and Early Adolescents' Orientation toward Peers. *Developmental Psychology*. **29**: 622-632.
- [5] Gershoff, E. T., Grogan-Kaylor, A., Lansford, J. E., Chang, L., Zelli, A. and Deater-Deckard, K. *et al.*, 2010. Parent Discipline Practices in An International Sample: Associations With Child Behaviour and Moderation by Perceived Normativeness. *Child Development*. **81**: 487-502.
- [6] Grogan-Kaylor, A. 2004. The Effect of Corporal Punishment and the Growth Trajectory of Children's Antisocial Behaviour. *Child Maltreatment*. **85**: 745-755.

- [7] Hay, I., Byrne, M., and Butler, C. 2000. Evaluation of a Conflict-Resolution and Problem-Solving Programme to Enhance Adolescents' Self-Concept. *British Journal of Guidance and Counselling*. **28**: 100–113.
- [8] Kakar, S. 1978. *The Inner World: A Psychoanalytical Study of Childhood and Society in India*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- [9] Kiran and Singh, M.B. 1982. Factors Affecting the Parental Acceptance of Pre-School Children. *Asian journal of psychology and education*. **9**: 21-28.
- [10] Larson, R. and Richards, M. H. 1991. Daily Companionship in Childhood and Adolescence: Changing Developmental Contexts. *Child development*. **62**: 284-300.
- [11] Salovey, P. Mayor, J. D., Goldman, S. L., Turvey, C., and Palfai, T. P. 2002. Emotional Attention, Clarity and Repair: Exploring Emotional Intelligence Using the Trait Meta-Mood Scale.
- [12] Simmons, R. G., Burgeson, R., Carlton-Ford, S. and Blyth, D. A. 1987. The Impact of Cumulative Changes in Early Adolescence. *Child Development*. **58**: 1220–1234.
- [13] Steinberg, L. D. and Silverberg, S. B. 1987. The Vicissitudes of Autonomy. *Journal of Child Development*. **57**: 841-851.
- [14] Walter, D. S. 1974. *Human Development*. (6th Ed.). Mc Graw Hill: New York.
- [15] Wentzel, K. R. and Battle, A. A. 2001. School Relationships and School Adjustment. In Urdan, T., and Pajares, F. (eds.), *Adolescence and Education: General Issues in the Education of Adolescence*. Information Age Publishing. Greenwich. pp93–118.